

Assessment of Noise Levels in Working with Welding and CNC Milling Machines in Mechanical Workshops of an Academic Institute

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(Received February 08, 2024; Revised February 21, 2025; Accepted April 01, 2025)

Abstract: Occupational noise is one of the most hazardous factors in a working environment, including mechanical workshops equipped with industrial robots, CNC machines, etc. under computer numerical control systems that are now indispensable in a modern technological environment. This necessitates noise assessment of such workshops under-industrial setup in academic institutes as well. In the present study of Robotics Lab and CNC Lab, the equivalent continuous noise level (L_{Aeq}) exceeded the permissible limit of 75 dB at some locations/areas, including the operator location at Mig Welding (79.62 dB, 6.16 % higher), and in Common area (75.37 dB, 0.49 % higher) during the parallel operations of all the three welding machines; whereas, L_{Aeq} values were within permissible level in CNC Lab in working areas. However, the maximum (L_{Amax}) and peak (L_{Apeak}) noise levels were above 85 dB in the production and non-production sections of both the labs and have the potential to cause hearing loss to the workers. The representative spatial noise maps of both Labs were also created using interpolation tools by using ArcGIS 10.7.1 software by adopting the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) technique to draw spatial distribution diagrams of noise levels, so as to reveal the noise hotspots in the Labs. The observed noise levels in the present study are lower than the similar reported studies possibly due to the adoption of less noisy super-automatic machines. However, the noise hotspots necessitate the suggested implications-specific preventive and corrective measures that include incorporating/adopting Kaizen techniques, noise masking, white noise machines, avoiding parallel operation of machines, hearing protectors, and double-glazed windows to reduce noise transmission to adjoining academic area.

Keywords: ArcGIS; CNC lab; equivalent continuous noise levels; inverse distance weighting; noise assessment; noise maps; robotics lab

1. Introduction

Occupational noise is the level of acoustic energy that is exposed to a worker's auditory pathway while they are working in a particular industry or industrial setup. Its increasing prevalence is one of the major environmental issues in all parts of the world^{1), 2)}, developed as well as developing nations^{3), 4)}. Noise pollution is not a mere inconvenience, but a cacophony having an adverse impact on the environment and quality of life⁵⁾. Exposure to high noise levels is one of the most hazardous factors in working environments – be it factory^{6), 7)}, workshop⁸⁾, academic⁹⁾, or research environment¹⁰⁾. Occupational noise exposure accounts for about 16% of disabling hearing

loses¹¹⁾. Occupational noise has many adverse effects on health (both physiological and psychological), performance, and productivity in any work field^{12), 13), 14)}. Among the many health effects, damage to the auditory system leading to temporary and permanent hearing loss^{15), 16)} is the most important consequence of chronic noise exposure – particularly in mechanical workshops and/or industries^{17), 18)}. If the noise level is 85 dB or above, hearing protective devices¹⁹⁾ have been recommended to safeguard the auditory damage^{20), 21)}.

In a mechanical workshop, the machine (M/c) noise is produced by its moving and mating parts, the interaction of machine tools and work-pieces, and the handling of finished and semi-finished products^{13), 22)}. A noise

exposure study of three public Technical and Vocational Education Training (TVET) institutes in Malaysia providing skill development in furniture manufacturing, metal fabrication technology, and automotive technology reported daily noise exposure levels between 75.3-103.7 dB(A) for diverse tasks or activities²³). A similar study of the Technical Education shops (TES) in Canadian High Schools, reported noise levels in the range of 80-100 dBA for metal-working, wood-working, and automotive workshops²⁴). In a welder workplace, high noise levels are reported during Tig welding (94.7 dBA) and FSW welding (82.7-83.6 dBA)²⁵). In a similar study of a carpentry workshop at Technical University in Romania, noise levels in the range of 82.35-86.29 dBA are reported²⁶). Another study of the workshop and structural labs (involving milling, lathing, grinding, and other such activities) reported noise levels in the range of 75-90 dBA in the workplace²⁷). The machining workshops at Kenyan Universities reported noise levels >85 dB(A) for 72% of machining activities, out of which 36.4% have >90 dB(A)²⁸). High noise levels have also been reported from other similar environments – such as small-scale industries²⁹, 30).

With a momentum towards ‘smart manufacturing’³¹) or ‘industry 4.0’ (I4.0T)³²), industrial robots, robotic arms, CNC (Computer Numerical Control) machines³³), and mechanized equipment are indispensable in the modern technological environment for high-volume productivity in industries, skill-development or hands-on training in academic and research institutes, controlling occupational health problems¹⁸, 34) and reducing noise emission³⁵, 36). However, metal processing with robotic and CNC machine tools (welding, lathes, milling & turning machines, and others) always poses certain health risks, and noise is one such risk⁶, 21, 37). Everyone who works in a workshop or laboratory in an academic institute under industrial-setting may be vulnerable to noise levels if they frequently exceed the permitted limits over a longer duration³⁸). Therefore, monitoring, assessment, and evaluation of noise levels is exceptionally important in industrial conditions³⁹), that is in Robotics Welding and CNC Labs that can serve as the basis for using different methods of noise reduction or to recommend personal hearing protection for operator and/or worker, if required.

The principle objectives of the present study are –

- to quantify the noise produced by metal cutting machines with identical kinematics and geometrical properties used in CNC computer numerical control systems, and robotic control welding tools;
- to monitor and analyze the noise levels while the machines operate individually and simultaneously;
- to identify noise hot spots using representative spatial noise maps prepared by using ArcGIS software; and

- to identify the implications and suggested remedial measures in view of an academic environment.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study was carried out for Robotics Lab (floor area = 189.02 sq. m.) and CNC Lab (floor area = 121.38 sq. m.) located adjacently in Siemens Centre of Excellence at National Institute of Technology Kurukshetra, Haryana (India). These Labs are utilized for academic, research, training, and consultancy purposes by students as well as faculty. The Robotics Lab has three machines (robotic arms) for different types of welding, namely Tig (Tungsten Inert Gas) Welding (KR10-R1420), Mig (Metal Inert Gas) Welding (KR10-R1420), and Spot Welding (KR210-R2700); whereas, the CNC Lab has two CNC Machines for automate milling (Maxmill: 828D) and turning (Maxturn: 828D) for stable and robust metal cutting and finishing³³), and one Robotic Handling Arm (KR16-R1610) for pick and place purposes in the handling Cell/Section. The operating areas of the machines in both the labs are on one side of the respective halls, and epoxy flooring has been provided due to its toughness and suitability for the industrial environment⁴⁰, 41). The photographs of both the Labs/Machines and the layout plan (dimensions in meters) marked with the noise monitoring locations are presented in Figure 1.

The noise in the Robotics Lab or CNC Lab is not only the result of the operation of an individual machine but also their parallel operation (i.e. in a group or combination). So, in accordance with the objective of the study, noise measurements were carried out in different production areas with different machines and in non-production areas as well¹²). A total of 41 shop-floor monitoring locations (Robotics Lab: 20, and CNC Lab: 21) were identified representing 5 key areas in the working place/shop-floor of respective Labs during the operation of an individual M/c as well as combination/group of machines in parallel⁶, 42), 43). The identified and designated noise monitoring locations include – the operator’s position, i.e. the nearest location where the operator stands and runs the machine (A); machine area, i.e. expected noisy locations near the M/c motor in case of CNC machines, and right or left side of the M/c in case of Robotic welding machines (B); backside of the Robotic welding machines, or sitting area in CNC Lab (C); common area, representing the central part of the Lab area expected to have maximum noise level during the simultaneous operation of all machines in a Lab (D); and pathway, perpendicular point on the pathway from the operator’s position (E).

2.2. Measurement of noise indices

A digital sound level meter (SLM) – CEL-620B1 (Casella,

Fig. 1: Layout plan of Robotics Lab and CNC Labs with noise monitoring locations, and images of the Labs

UK) was used in the present study. The specifications and accuracies of the SLM sensor are – research grade Class-1 (Type 1) with level linearity error less than ± 1.1 dB, 1/1 octave band with a frequency response range of 6 to 20 Hz, measurement range between 0 to 140.2 dB(A), and operational temperature range from -10°C to $+50^{\circ}\text{C}$. The Noise monitoring was done using ‘A’ frequency weighting network and ‘fast time’ response mode. ‘Fast time’ response was selected because on the shop-floor the fluctuation of noise due to the working of machines is very high which needs to be assessed⁴⁴). The SLM was held at a height of 1.5 m above the ground with the microphone directed towards the noise source⁴⁵). Further, the SLM was held 1.0 m away from the machine’s vertically projected plan for measurements around M/c, that is operator’s position, and locations near the machine such as near the motor, right, left, or backside of the M/c as per IS 10988 standards⁴²). The SLM was calibrated at 114 dB (A) using a Casella CEL-120/1 Class-1 acoustic calibrator by following the instrument’s handbook before and after one

Table 1: Machine(s) running time and noise monitoring time

Lab	Operating M/c	M/c Running Time (seconds)	Noise Monitoring Time (seconds)
Robotics Lab	Tig Welding	120	120
	Mig Welding	90	90
	Spot Welding	60	60
	Tig, Mig & Spot Welding	60 - 120	60
CNC Lab	Maxmill	180	180
	Maxturn	180	180
	Robotic Handling Arm	180	180
	Maxmill, Maxturn & Robotic Handling Arm	180	180

Table 2: Indian ambient air quality standards in respect of noise

Area	Category of Area / Zone	Permissible Limits in L_{Aeq} dB	
		Day Time 06:00 am to 10:00 pm	Night Time (10:00 pm to 06:00 am
A	Industrial	75	70
B	Commercial	65	55
C	Residential	55	45
D	Silence	50	40

set of noise measurements.

Noise monitoring was carried out in an industrial shop-floor environment inside the Robotics Lab and CNC Lab from January to February 2023 during working hours in the daytime. Continuous monitoring was done for 3 minutes' duration per run at designated locations in the CNC Lab, and 1 to 2 minutes' duration per run at designated locations in Robotics Lab depending on the operational cycle of welding M/c (Table 1). In the case of simultaneous operation of all three welding machines having varying running times, noise assessment was done for 60 seconds, that is the duration in which all three machines were in operational/running mode. For noise monitoring at various designated locations during the operation of machine(s), the respective machine(s) were operated with the same type of job with the same material.

monitoring location and the average value was considered so as to reduce the chances of error. Thus, accounting for a total of 123 noise monitoring runs. To accurately measure the noise variation during the operation of M/c, it was ensured that the machine gets stabilized on a constant vibration.

Due to fluctuations in the surrounding noise levels, equivalent continuous noise level (L_{eq}) is the preferred method to describe sound levels that vary over time to have a single decibel (dB) value that takes into account the total energy over the period of time of interest⁴⁶. So, the following noise indices were considered and recorded by the SLM and subsequently used for noise analysis in the present study:

L_{Aeq} : Equivalent continuous noise level with A-weighted frequency, in decibels (dB).

L_{Amax} : Maximum A-weighted frequency noise level with a fast response (125 milliseconds), in decibels(dB).

L_{Amin} : Minimum A-weighted frequency noise level with a fast response (125 milliseconds), in decibels(dB).

L_{Apeak} : Highest instantaneous noise level with A-weighted frequency and no time weighting, in decibels (dB).

The average L_{Aeq} values and other noise indices, for a set of three measurements at each location, were computed as a logarithmic average of the relevant values by using the following formula¹⁰:

Table 3: Average noise indices at designated locations in Robotics Lab

Operating M/c	Monitored Location	Code	Average Noise Indices (dB)			
			L_{Aeq} (SE)	L_{Amax} (SE)	L_{Amin} (SE)	L_{Apeak} (SE)
Tig Welding	Operator	A	66.30 (±0.24)	76.13 (±0.35)	61.10 (±0.32)	91.68 (±0.67)
	Right side of M/c	B	64.54 (±0.39)	74.46 (±0.29)	59.93 (±0.53)	88.73 (±0.49)
	Backside of M/c	C	64.47 (±0.44)	75.04 (±0.34)	62.42 (±0.17)	91.49 (±0.47)
	Common area	D	62.53 (±0.37)	66.25 (±0.15)	61.08 (±0.27)	77.94 (±0.12)
	Pathway	E	63.97 (±0.39)	72.34 (±0.34)	61.03 (±0.49)	85.37 (±0.50)
Mig Welding	Operator	A	79.63 (±0.37)	87.33 (±0.53)	56.48 (±0.27)	108.55 (±0.36)
	Left side of M/c	B	74.75 (±0.16)	82.59 (±0.20)	60.15 (±0.13)	102.05 (±0.13)
	Right side of M/c	B	75.79 (±0.20)	84.89 (±0.18)	60.93 (±0.21)	104.85 (±0.17)
	Common area	D	74.17 (±0.24)	84.37 (±0.24)	57.17 (±0.24)	108.90 (±0.22)
	Pathway	E	67.98 (±0.13)	76.48 (±0.13)	56.94 (±0.11)	95.48 (±0.13)
Spot Welding	Operator	A	66.79 (±0.44)	77.09 (±0.42)	57.04 (±0.47)	87.70 (±0.43)
	Right side of M/c	B	66.57 (±0.39)	73.53 (±0.37)	61.95 (±0.27)	84.00 (±0.55)
	Backside of M/c	C	63.78 (±0.35)	69.61 (±0.15)	56.38 (±0.15)	81.95 (±0.27)
	Common area	D	63.41 (±0.25)	69.46 (±0.30)	57.50 (±0.30)	82.57 (±0.32)
	Pathway	E	64.80 (±0.49)	74.48 (±0.35)	58.43 (±0.37)	86.60 (±0.39)
Tig, Mig & Spot Welding	Operator: Spot Welding	A	72.82 (±0.52)	82.04 (±0.54)	61.19 (±0.54)	93.87 (±0.44)
	Operator: Mig Welding	A	79.62 (±0.27)	86.65 (±0.35)	56.25 (±0.16)	109.55 (±0.35)
	Operator: Tig Welding	A	72.51 (±0.40)	82.43 (±0.49)	58.62 (±0.29)	104.04 (±0.45)
	Common area	D	75.37 (±0.38)	86.59 (±0.28)	59.67 (±0.54)	108.53 (±0.37)
	Pathway	E	68.91 (±0.38)	78.60 (±0.38)	60.14 (±0.45)	97.85 (±0.35)

Further, a set of three measurements was taken at each

$$L_{Aeq} = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n 10^{\frac{L_i}{10}} \right] \quad (1)$$

where, n is the number of observations and L_i is the noise level.

During the noise monitoring study, an aluminum metal work-piece was used for desired cutting and finishing operations in Maxmill and Maxturn CNC machines. A uniform rotation of the spindle in RPM (rotation per minute) and uniform feed rate for metal milling and turning were maintained for the entire duration while working with both the CNC M/c.

The recorded data of SLM was downloaded to a personal computer daily at the end of the experiment and processed by using Microsoft Excel. The measured data was then statistically analyzed and compared with prescribed permissible limits for the industrial category (daytime) as per Indian standards^{47), 48), 49)}, as presented in Table 2.

2.3. Analysis approach

The analysis has been carried out as per the objectives of the study covering –

- preparatory work: such as deciding and defining the noise measurement points and their locations in

respective labs, operating the machine, and defining its parameters;

- diagnostic evaluation: such as noise measurements, computation, evaluation, and analysis;
- drawing inferences: such as comparison of results to the permissible levels as per Indian noise standards for industrial areas/zones during the daytime;
- noise maps and identification of noise hotspots; and
- conclusions and suggestions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Noise analysis of robotics lab

The computed average noise indices, along with standard error (SE), at the designated noise monitoring locations in the Robotics Lab have been presented in Table 3. The SE ranges between ± 0.13 to ± 0.52 for average L_{Aeq} values, and (Table 3) indicates lower variability across multiple observations. The average noise levels (L_{Aeq} , in dB) along with the prescribed Indian standards for the industrial category have been presented in Figure 2 for graphical interpretation.

Fig. 2: Average equivalent continuous noise levels (L_{Aeq}) at designated locations during the operation of welding machines in Robotics Lab

3.1.1. Machines operating individually

During the operation of Tig Welding, the L_{Aeq} values (Fig. 2a) at all the locations were observed within the permissible level of 75 dB. The maximum noise levels (L_{Amax}) were in the range of 66.25-75.04 dB with peak noise levels (L_{Apeak}) in the range of 77.94-91.68 dB (Table 3). The highest noise level ($L_{Aeq} = 66.30$ dB) was observed at the operator’s location with a peak value of 91.68 dB. During the operation of Mig Welding, the L_{Aeq} values (Fig. 2b) at the operator’s location were highest (79.63 dB) exceeding the permissible level of 75 dB by 4.63 dB (6.17 %), and marginally exceeding by 0.79 dB (1.05 %) at the location on right side of machine (M/c); however, the noise levels were within the permissible level at other three locations. The L_{Amax} were in the range of 76.48-87.33 dB and L_{Apeak} in the range of 95.48-108.90 dB (Table 3). During the operation of Spot Welding, the L_{Aeq} values (Fig. 2c) at all the locations were well within the permissible level; whereas, L_{Amax} were in the range of 69.46-77.09 dB with L_{Apeak} in the range of 81.95-87.70 dB (Table 3).

3.1.2. Machines operating simultaneously

During the simultaneous operation of all three welding machines (Tig, Mig and Spot), the L_{Aeq} values (Fig. 2d) at Mig Welding operator’s location was highest (79.62 dB) exceeding the permissible level by 5.62 dB (6.16 %) with

a peak noise level of 109.55 dB, and marginally exceeding in common area ($L_{Aeq} = 75.37$ dB); however, the noise levels were within limits at other three locations. During simultaneous operation, the L_{Amax} was in the range of 78.60-86.65 dB and L_{Apeak} in the range of 93.87-109.55dB.

3.1.3. Intra-comparison of welding machines

The intra-comparison revealed that the Spot welding process was quietest followed by Tig welding, and average L_{Aeq} values were within permissible limits during their operations. However, the Mig welding process was noisiest due to which the noise levels exceeded the permissible limits at its operator’s location during individual and parallel operations. Also, there was a lot of fluctuation of noise during Mig and Tig welding. Mig Welding process was noisier probably due to the reason that it can weld thicker metals and is based on a continuous feeding wire mechanism.

3.2. Noise analysis of CNC lab

The computed average noise indices and standard error (SE) at the designated noise monitoring locations in the CNC Lab have been presented in Table 4. The SE ranges between ± 0.05 to ± 0.38 for average L_{Aeq} values (Table 4) indicate lower variability across multiple observations. The average noise levels (L_{Aeq} , in dB) along with the permissible levels as per prescribed Indian standards have

Table 4: Average noise indices at designated locations in CNC Lab

Operating M/c	Monitored Location	Code	Average Noise Indices (dB)			
			L_{Aeq} (SE)	L_{Amax} (SE)	L_{Amin} (SE)	L_{Apeak} (SE)
Maxmill	Operator	A	70.68 (±0.35)	77.52 (±0.58)	63.21 (±0.26)	91.63 (±1.22)
	M/c motor	B	75.39 (±0.19)	83.65 (±1.60)	68.61 (±1.66)	98.14 (±1.09)
	Sitting area	C	72.16 (±0.20)	79.11 (±0.65)	67.22 (±0.37)	99.77 (±2.15)
	Common area	D	69.07 (±0.10)	75.50 (±0.78)	63.57 (±0.23)	91.19 (±1.35)
	Pathway	E	69.14 (±0.11)	75.67 (±0.89)	63.30 (±0.00)	90.75 (±1.52)
Maxturn	Operator	A	73.14 (±0.08)	77.65 (±0.27)	71.47 (±0.08)	94.10 (±1.24)
	M/c motor	B	80.93 (±0.20)	86.59 (±0.37)	77.67 (±0.98)	100.24 (±0.51)
	Sitting area	C	72.90 (±0.06)	82.92 (±1.96)	71.13 (±0.20)	95.63 (±1.96)
	Common area	D	71.84 (±0.07)	78.44 (±0.71)	69.21 (±0.86)	91.11 (±0.86)
	Pathway	E	71.34 (±0.05)	80.20 (±1.41)	69.97 (±0.08)	95.75 (±1.80)
Robotic Handling Arm	Operator	A	65.10 (±0.22)	93.01 (±0.25)	62.73 (±0.22)	93.18 (±0.60)
	M/c motor	B	67.38 (±0.34)	68.54 (±0.25)	66.79 (±0.42)	80.89 (±0.49)
	Sitting area	C	60.63 (±0.38)	70.58 (±0.33)	60.89 (±0.37)	88.49 (±0.28)
	Common area	D	62.28 (±0.13)	65.72 (±0.27)	61.27 (±0.08)	80.10 (±0.49)
	Pathway	E	61.57 (±0.31)	64.94 (±0.23)	60.65 (±0.40)	79.79 (±0.20)
Maxmill, Maxturn & Robotic Handling Arm	Operator: Maxmill	A	72.27 (±0.23)	74.31 (±0.34)	71.70 (±0.44)	94.33 (±0.30)
	Operator: Maxturn	A	73.63 (±0.38)	74.40 (±0.32)	72.63 (±0.30)	95.74 (±0.41)
	Operator: Robotic Handling Arm	A	71.36 (±0.37)	73.49 (±0.20)	71.75 (±0.47)	94.11 (±0.10)
	Sitting area	C	73.47 (±0.10)	84.02 (±2.03)	72.16 (±0.19)	95.86 (±1.75)
	Common area	D	72.10 (±0.21)	79.31 (±1.71)	69.58 (±0.90)	91.98 (±1.44)
	Pathway	E	72.05 (±0.13)	84.34 (±0.50)	71.02 (±0.34)	98.01 (±0.45)

been shown in Fig. 3.

3.2.1. Machines operating individually

During the operation of Maxmill, the L_{Aeq} values (Fig. 3a) at all the locations were observed within the permissible level of 75 dB, except at the M/c motor location where the noise level exceeded marginally by 0.39 dB (0.52 %). The maximum noise levels (L_{Amax}) were in the range of 75.50-83.65 dB with peak noise levels (L_{Apeak}) in the range of 90.75-99.77 dB (Table 4). During the operation of Maxturn also, the L_{Aeq} values (Fig. 3b) at all the locations were observed within the permissible level, except at M/c motor location where the noise level exceeded by 5.93 dB (7.91 %). The L_{Amax} were in the range of 77.65-86.59 dB with L_{Apeak} in the range of 91.11-100.24 dB (Table 4). The higher noise levels at M/c motor locations of both the CNC machines may be acceptable considering that no human presence is anticipated or required there. During the operation of the Robotic Handling Arm, the L_{Aeq} values (Figure 3c) at all the locations were well within the permissible level; whereas, the L_{Amax} were in the range of 64.94-93.01 dB with L_{Apeak} in the range of 79.79-93.18 dB (Table 3).

3.2.2. Machines operating simultaneously

During simultaneous operation of both the CNC machines

(Maxmill and Maxturn) and Robotic Handling Arm, the L_{Aeq} values (Figure 3d) were found to be within the permissible level of 75 dB at the respective operator locations, sitting and common areas as well as at the pathway. The L_{Amax} were in the range of 73.49-84.34 dB with L_{Apeak} in the range of 91.98-98.01 dB (Table 4).

3.2.3. Intra-comparison of CNC machines and robotic handling arm

The intra-comparison revealed that the operation of the handling cell was quietest; whereas, CNC machines were noisier due to the operation of cutting and finishing metal work-pieces. Maxtrum was noisier among both the CNC machines probably due to the reason that the process of cutting, turning, and threading (the work-piece rotates against a stationary cutting tool) is more intense than the milling and grinding process by Maxmill. In the Handling cell, there was not much noise released as the Robotic Handling Arm was made for pick and place purposes only.

3.3. Comparative noise analysis of robotics and CNC labs

As presented and analyzed above, the noise levels were observed to be higher during the parallel operations of machines than individually at various locations – production and non-production areas, in both labs. The

Fig. 3: Average equivalent continuous noise levels (L_{Aeq}) at designated locations during the operation of CNC machines and Robotic Handling Arm in CNC Lab

comparative noise analysis during the parallel operation of machines in the Robotics Lab and CNC Lab, Figure 2d and Figure 3d respectively, revealed that the Robotics Lab was noisier than the CNC Lab. Further, the operators in the Robotics Lab were exposed to higher noise levels ($L_{Aeq} = 72.51$ to 79.62 dB) than in the CNC Lab ($L_{Aeq} = 71.36$ to 73.63 dB). In fact, the L_{Aeq} value exceeded the permissible limit of 75 dB at two locations in the Robotics Lab – Operator: Mig Welding (79.62 dB, 6.16 % higher) and Common area (75.37 dB, 0.49 % higher); whereas, the noise levels were well within the permissible limits in CNC Lab at all locations including Operator’s locations and Common area.

The overall average noise indices were computed for both labs during parallel operations of machines in respective labs so as to have overall comparative noise indices at a glance, and presented in Figure 4. It can be observed that the Robotics Lab was noisier to the noise indices – L_{Aeq} , L_{Amax} and L_{Apeak} . The lower L_{Amin} value in Robotics Lab has been due to a large variation in noise levels as discussed earlier.

3.4. Noise maps of robotics and CNC labs

The representative spatial noise maps of Robotics and CNC Labs were created using interpolation tools by using ArcGIS 10.7.1 software. For this, the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) technique was utilized to prepare spatial distribution diagrams of noise levels^{50), 51)}. IDW is recommended to evaluate values at unmeasured locations based on the values of surrounding measured locations⁵²⁾. This method computes the weighted average of the

Fig. 4: Average noise indices in Robotics and CNC Labs

measured values, wherein the weights decrease as the distance from the predicted location increases and is represented by equation (1) as under:

$$Z_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times Z_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad (2)$$

where, Z_p is the estimated value, w_i is the assigned weight, n is the number of measured values.

The noise levels (L_{Aeq}) of the monitored locations were used as the input data in preparing the representative noise maps for machines operating individually and simultaneously.

A glance at the noise maps of Robotics Lab (Figure 5),

Fig. 5: Interpolation of noise level of Robotics Lab

showed noise hotspots ($L_{Aeq} > 75$ dB) during the operation of Mig welding machine, both whether operating individually (Figure 5b) or simultaneously with Tig and Spot welding machines (Figure 5d). This necessitates the usage of ear protection devices by the operator(s) as well as persons in the operating and common areas. However, the noise levels were within permissible limits in the sitting area for the staff and pathway.

In CNC Lab (Figure 6), the noise hotspots ($L_{Aeq} > 75$ dB) were observed in and around the operating areas of Maxmill (Figure 6a) and Maxtrum (Fig 6b) during their operation – individually or simultaneously (Figure 6d). This necessitates the noise abatement and other measures in the noise hot spots of the Robotics and CNC Labs (Figure 6).

3.5. Implications and Suggestions

The results of the study revealed that average L_{Aeq} exceeded the permissible limit only at some locations in the Robotics and CNC Labs, particularly during the parallel operations of machines. However, the maximum (L_{Amax}) and peak (L_{Apeak}) noise levels were above 85 dB which raises occupational health and other issues, such as

- annoyance and communication interference;
- potential to develop hearing loss in the exposed persons, particularly the operators; and
- transmission of noise from the labs to the adjoining academic area (silence zone) that may affect the teaching-learning process.

In view of the implications, the following measures have

been suggested –

- avoid parallel operations of machines in the lab, and turn-off extra machines immediately after their use;
- the sitting area for the staff of CNC Lab (between Maxtrum and Robotic Handling Arm) be relocated to a relatively quieter location based on the noise map of the lab;
- proper working and maintenance of machines and noise-suppressing features as per schedule;
- hearing protectors (ear muffs, ear plugs, etc.), particularly the operators during working in noisy sections;
- sound-absorbing materials in both labs can be augmented;
- double glazing of windows to counter transmission loss to the nearby academic area⁸⁾;

Kaizen Techniques can be used for continuous improvement of noise reduction⁵³⁾;

- a passive sound may be created inside or near the labs to mask the annoying sounds, such as – hanging wind chimes; background light-music of running-water, etc.; switching on a fan; running a small water-feature; etc.²²⁾;

- a white noise machine can be created by a continuum of frequencies equally distributed over the whole hearing range, as used in healthcare applications – to treat hypocrisies, and to camouflage the annoyance caused by tinnitus in the ear occurring without any stimulus; and
- working staff be subjected to hearing tests and other health tests periodically.

3.6. Comparison with previously reported studies

The results of previously reported studies in similar environments, such as vocational training centers,

Fig. 6: Interpolation of noise level of CNC Lab

Table 5: Comparative noise levels, L_{Aeq} (in dB), of reported studies in workplaces/labs

Organization	Lab / Workplace	Task / Machines	L_{Aeq} (in dB)	Reference
Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Institutes in Malaysia	Furniture manufacturing,	Sharpening Tool Points	90.4	Rahim, <i>et al.</i> ²³⁾
		Wood cutting, edging, rounding or curving	84.2 to 85.4	
	Metal Fabrication technology.	TIG and MIG Welding	89.6	
		SMAW Welding	89.4	
		Grinding and Cutting	95.7	
		Cutting-Plate/Sheet (Oxy)	89.5	
	Automotive technology	Cutting-Bar (Cut-off Saw)	103.7	
		Metal Work-Cutting & Grinding	91.0	
University of Montenegro	Welder workplace	TIG (Tungsten Inert Gas) welding	94.7	Lukinenko <i>et al.</i> ²⁵⁾
		FSW (Friction Stir Welding) welding	82.7 to 83.6	
Technical University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania	Carpentry workshop	Cutting, milling, shaping, etc.	82.35 to 86.29	Musca <i>et al.</i> ²⁶⁾
Industrial Workers, Malaysia	Metal fabrication		90	Tahir <i>et al.</i> ³⁰⁾
College of Engineering, University of Al-Mustansiriyah, Iraq.	Workshop and Structure Labs	Grinding, bar cutting, milling, and lething machines in workshop lab. Electric sieve, concrete mixer, compressive strength testing m/c, etc. in structure lab.	75 to 90	Ibrahim ²⁷⁾
Canadian High Schools, British Columbia, Canada	Technical Education Shops	Metal-working, wood-working, and Automotive.	80 to 100	Summan <i>et al.</i> ²⁴⁾
Small-scale Industries, Saudi Arabia	Metal processing		89.1 +/- 3.3	ElSharkawy ²⁹⁾
	Foundries		86.4 +/- 2	
Workshops and Laboratories in Kenyan Universities	Machining workshops	Milling, grinding, drilling, lathe work, etc.	>85 dB(A) for 72% of machining activities, out of which 36.4% have >90 dB(A)	Onyango <i>et al.</i> ²⁸⁾
NIT Kurukshetra, India.	Robotics lab	Tig, Mig and Spot welding	62.53 to 79.63	Present study
	CNC lab	Milling, turning, cutting and finishing, and handling.	60.63 to 80.93	

workshops/laboratories, and small-scale industries are compiled and tabulated in Table 5. The comparison revealed that the workplace (Robotics and CNC labs) of the present study is less noisy than the other reported studies with similar tasks and/or machines. This is possibly due to the reason that the machines are super-automatic having direct motion motors using fewer mechanical components, and are provided with noise enclosures, sound absorbents, and anti-vibration mounts. This suggests that smart manufacturing, which is a technology-driven approach to improve manufacturing performance must incorporate the use of silent machines in controlling occupational health problems and reducing noise emission.

4. Conclusion

The present study revealed that equivalent continuous noise level (L_{Aeq}) exceeded the permissible limit only at some locations in the Robotics and CNC Labs, particularly

during the parallel operations of machines). However, the maximum (L_{Amax}) and peak (L_{Apeak}) noise levels were above 85 dB which has the potential to develop hearing loss, particularly the operators. The other implications are annoyance, communication interference, and transmission of noise from the labs to the adjoining academic area (silence zone) that may affect the teaching-learning process.

The study firmly asserts that integrating silent machines into smart manufacturing is essential for enhancing manufacturing performance. This approach effectively tackles occupational health issues and significantly reduces noise emissions.

Like any other study, the present study also has certain limitations, including a shorter duration of noise monitoring, and lacking of an 8-hour noise exposure study of the staff (particularly of operators) using a personal dosimeter as required in an industrial setup. It is, therefore,

recommended to address these aspects in future studies.

Acknowledgments

The present study was accomplished in the Robotics and CNC Labs of Siemens Centre of Excellence at the National Institute of Technology Kurukshetra. The authors express gratitude towards the staff of both labs for their all-around support during this study.

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